

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Natural enemies of brown planthopper and green leafhopper in India

T. M. Manjunath, P. S. Rai, and Gavi Gowda, University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station, V.C. Farm, Mandya, Karnataka, India

Severe infestations of the rice brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix nigropictus* occurred in several localities in Mandya, Karnataka, during the summer (Jan.–May) and kharif (May–Dec.) paddy seasons of 1976. Hoppers at all growth stages were collected and separated into cages. The predators found in association with them were placed in cages with the hoppers and their feeding on them was observed. The natural enemies listed below were common to the BPH and GLH.

EGG PARASITES

- Hymenoptera
Trichogrammatidae *Oligosita* sp.

NYMPHAL/ADULT PARASITES

- Hymenoptera
Dryinidae *Echthrodelpfax fairchildii* Fallen
Haplogonatopus sp.

PREDATORS

- Coleoptera
Coccinellidae *Coccinella arcuata* F.
- Hemiptera
Anthocoridae *Amphiaraeus constrictus* Stal. (*hulvscens* Walk.)
Miridae *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter
Tytthus parviceps Reuter
- Hymenoptera
Formicidae *Camponotus* sp. 1
Camponotus sp. 2 (*fulvomarginatus* group)

PATHOGEN

- Entomophthorales
Entomophthoraceae *Entomophthora* sp.
- Amphibia
Anura, Ranidae *Rana limnocaris limnocaris* Wieg.

A few individuals of three Scelionid species, *Baeus*, *Gryon*, and *Oxyscelio* sp.,

also emerged in the tubes containing portions of leafsheaths bearing BPH and GLH eggs, but their exact status will have to be confirmed. Three unidentified species of spiders were also common in rice fields.

C. lividipennis was the most important predator. The dryinids gave up to 51 %

Two nematode parasites of rice brown Planthopper in India

T. M. Manjunath, junior entomologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station, C.D. Farm, Mandya, Karnataka, India

Several natural enemies of the rice brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* have recently been reported in India.

While continuing the survey, the author recorded two more nematode species as parasites. Both belong to the genus *Hexameris* of the family *Mermithidae*.

One nematode was minute (about 0.50 mm long) and scarce; it was reared on only three planthopper adults. More than 100 juveniles emerged from a single host. The other nematode, a Mermithid, was fairly large and common. The parasitized host had a greatly distended abdomen (Fig. 1) and fell on the ground before the parasite emerged. Only one nematode emerged from a single host (Fig. 2). Fifteen freshly emerged juvenile nematodes had an average length of

4.84 mm (range, 4.20 to 5.90 mm) and an average width of 0.308 mm (0.286 to 0.315 mm). The nematode was reared from both brachypterous and macropterous males and females, but field parasitism of brachypterous females was consistently higher than that of other forms (see table).

parasitism of BPH. Studies on the bioecology of these natural enemies are in progress. The authors are grateful to the Director, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, for identification of the specimens.

1. A brown planthopper (brachypterous female) parasitized by a Mermithid.
2. The nematode that has just emerged from brown planthopper.

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Parasitism of brown planthopper^a (BPH) by a Mermithid. Karnataka, India, 1977.

Month	BPH examined (no.)					Parasitism (%)				
	Females		Males		Total	Females		Males		Total
	BM		BM			BM	BM			
October (2nd half)	70	43	6	32	151	12.9	4.6	0	3.1	8.0
November	94	115	20	53	282	33.0	10.4	15.0	9.4	18.1
December (1st week)	15	25	0	20	60	33.3	12.0	0	10.0	16.7

^aB = Brachypterous form; m = macropterous form.